

A Study on Impact of Digital Payments of Retail Stores in Hyderabad City

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Abstract: The purpose of this research study is to examine how is in Telangana state City's retail management is affected by cashless transaction technologies. The study used an exploratory methodology to offer insightful information about the ways in which different kinds of retail enterprises have been impacted by the adoption of systems for cashless transactions. The study's conclusions, derived from 100 shops in Hyderabad City, show that cashless transaction systems have a favorable effect on retail management. Along with notable cost reductions, the merchants have noted increased operational efficiency and transparency. The study's findings provide legislators and other stakeholders with crucial information that they can use to create programs and regulations that encourage the adoption of cashless transactions in the retail industry. The business models of small retail convenience stores in India are facing challenges due to the entry of major supermarkets and online merchants, as well as the increasing usage of digital technologies. This study examined the difficulties faced by small retail stores in the face of a deliberate government push towards digital payments, growing competition from big supermarkets and online retailers, and a qualitative methodology using the Technology-Organization-Environment framework. The study's issues include perceived loss of control, technology expenses, and low socioeconomic background of customers, supplier influence, tax and security concerns, bureaucracy, and low trust in external and regulatory environments. The adoption of digital technologies is also being hampered by inadequate physical and digital infrastructure, high costs, and unreliable digital technology.

Key Words: Digital Payment's, Digital Technology, Technology Expenses. And Security Concern.

Introduction

Digital payments are More security, convenience, and control are provided to users of banking cards than with any other method of payment. Extreme freedom is further offered by the large selection of available cards, which include credit, debit, and prepaid card options. These cards offer two factors. verification for safe financial transactions, such as secure OTPs (one-time passwords) and PINs (personal information numbers). Payment cards enable consumers to make purchases in physical stores, online, through e-commerce, over the phone, via email order catalogues, and on the Internet. They make transactions more convenient for both buyers and sellers by saving them time and money. By supplying K.Y.C. (Know Your Customer) information to create an account, a debit card, a credit card, and a PIN, anyone can obtain

banking cards. These cards are accepted at Points of Sale (P.O.S.). devices, ATMs, Micro ATMs, stores, wallets, and PIN and OTP-based online and e-commerce transactions worldwide at a minimal cost or for free, provided by Indian banks. Establishing financial equality is essential in a nation like India where disparities can be significant. A primary motivation behind the government's discussion of Digital India and the Less Cash Economy was to increase the availability of inexpensive financial resources. The importance of digitization in the banking and financial sectors cannot be overstated. Even before the epidemic struck, digital banking and mobile payments had experienced a sharp increase in the global payment system, particularly in emerging nations. Thanks to affordable cell phones and fast internet, a robust e-commerce sector has been established in many economies. All types of fintech companies have benefited from these developments in digital infrastructure by building business models that are focused on offering a range of payment options, credit management, providing remittance services to people who don't have access to traditional financial networks or banking.

Digital Payment: "A general word that encompasses any electronic payment transaction. includes payments made using a computer or mobile device. In certain situations, card payments are regarded as digital payments. The phrase the term "mobile payment" is equally inclusive and covers a broad range of transaction kinds. which in some way make use of a mobile phone.

Current Status of Digital Payment in India: Currently, India offers a wide range of digital payment options, including prepaid payment instruments, ATM-based, point-of-sale terminals, USSD, wallet payments, AePS, Aadhaar Pay, NEFT, RTGS, mobile banking, UPI, IMPS, ECS Cr., NACH Cr., and credit card payments. Based on earlier research, it is evident that, in comparison to total cash retail payments, the percentage of digital payments in retail payment transactions is quite small. The data that is currently available demonstrates the state of digital payments in India.

Challenges Of Digital Payments in India: India's cash economy and growing retail digital payment usage indicate a change in the nation's attitude towards digital payments. The swift growth of digital payments for retail purposes is giving India's economy a boost and potential. The future of payments is being shaped by digital payments because of its increasing convenience, competitiveness, and acceptability. The full spectrum of user demands is met by both cash and non-cash payment methods, provided that these needs remain constant. India is converting to digital payment methods at a rapid pace. The regulator and participants attribute their success to many aspects, including trust (facilitated by measures like AFA), customer confidence (account settlement and no default risks), cheap access costs, and convenience (mobile payment systems that are simple to use). Have spent time trying to increase digital payments. Still, the nation has a way to go before its economy transitions from being mostly cash-based to being mostly digital.

Review of literature:

Adhikary, A., Diatha, K. S., Borah, S. B., & Sharma, A. (2021), in their research paper titled "How Does the Adoption of Digital Payment Technologies Influence Unorganized Retailers' Performance?" An investigation in an emerging market indicates that unorganised retailers can improve their performance by combining both card-based and app-based technologies, and that card-based and account-based technologies have a synergistic impact. Adoption improves the economic performance by 9.6% on average for unorganised retailers. Researchers try to understand the adoption of digital 81 payments technologies in emerging markets of the unorganised retail sector. Researchers have collected 403 samples from the unorganised retail sector to study the adoption of digital payment technologies to increase the revenue of establishments.

Mishra, V., Walsh, I., & Srivastava, A. (2021), they have conducted exploratory study titled "Merchants' adoption of mobile payment in emerging economies: the case of unorganised retailers in India" to examine the trends of digital adoption by unorganised retailers in India. Researchers have conducted the 56 semi-structured interviews with unorganised retailers. The researchers highlight the significance of technology, regulatory bodies, non-regulatory bodies, and retailer attitudes in an evolving mobile payment environment. Researchers found that Indian regulatory authorities are not the most powerful drivers in the spread of digital technology but also important market participants in the area of digital market. This study states the vital link that unorganised retailers make between enterprises and bottom-of-pyramid consumers, as well as between the state and its underprivileged residents, proving that such retailers are crucial in economic growth and technology-driven inclusion.

Meity (February, 2019), Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, Government of India published an e-book titled "Digital Bharat, Saksham Bharat-A Compendium on Digital India". Highlights of the book are: 1) 3.10 lakh digital services delivery centres have been established across the country to enable economical access to digital services such as pensions, 78 banking, insurance, and payments, particularly in rural areas; 2) The world's largest digital literacy initiative has been imparted under PMGDISHA to 1.45 crore people; 3) More than 120 BPO units have opened in India's small towns covering 20 states and two union territories. 4) The country has launched a hardware manufacturing promotion.5) A total of Rs. 6.21 lakh crore has been distributed through Aadhaar-based DBT to beneficiaries of 438 government schemes, resulting in savings of more than Rs. 1.1 lakh crore over the previous four years due to the elimination of fraudulent claimants.6) Over the last three years, Rs 5,295 crore in scholarships have been awarded through the National Scholarship Portal, which has 1.4 lakh students registered. People's interactions with the government to obtain various services have been streamlined through digital delivery of services, which has enhanced citizens' ease of living. The Compendium shows how India has become more digital. It also shows how ICT is improving the lives of India's 1.3 billion people both socially and economically.

Gupta, S. K., & Bansal, A. (2018), in their descriptive study titled "Young Customer's Attitude Towards Digital Banking with Special Reference to Public and Private Banks in Uttarakhand,"

they determine the consumers' overall happiness with the present online banking services and their perceptions of the overall service quality. Researchers highlight that digital banking allows customers to get more information in less time. Customer satisfaction is a key aspect to helping banks' ability to maintain a competitive advantage. The majority of India's leading banks have started to offer digital banking services. Researchers try to understand which factors influence customer satisfaction with digital banking services. Researchers found in their study after collecting the 120 responses through questionnaires that some customers are not aware about digital banking services, customers are concerned about their safety and security while doing digital banking transactions, and some customers are less educated which become the major hindrance in using digital services of banks. Researchers state that still people are not using all the available digital banking services due lack of awareness about technology and the internet.

Radhika, K. P., and Devi, P. A. (2018), in their research paper titled "Use of Electronic Payment Instruments and Effect on Cash Management", try to examine the adoption rate of electronic payment instruments by using the micro 79 level Baumol Tobin Model of demand for money. Researchers used the primary source of data collection and 400 responses were used from different zones for this study. According to the study, more than 50% of the participants preferred "cash-payment" for transactions valued at less than Rs.10,000 (PP 723), which indicates customers' preference for "low-value transactions" and using debit and credit cards had the greatest impact on "level of indebtedness" among the respondents, indicating that using cards for retail purchases considerably substituted cash.

Molly, C. (2017), highlights in her research paper titled "A Study on the Opportunities and Challenges of the Retail Sector in India" that since the majority of India's population is young, consumption is on the rise, which is one of the main reasons for the retail sector's growth and development. Due to the changes in tastes, preferences, lifestyles and shifting consumption patterns accordingly, the author recognised that demand, entrance hurdles, customer negotiating power, collection, and other factors are influencing the retail market. Indian retailers have a lot of problems with their supply chain, their ability to reach the rural market, their ability to use technology, their ability to make personalised selections, and their ability to keep in touch with their customers.

Jegan, K., & Kannan, D. N. (2017), in their research paper titled "Customer Expectation and Perception Towards Organized and Unorganized Retail", Jegan and Kannan (2017) state that moving/shifting from traditional businesses to organised retail businesses takes a long time. FDI is always a political issue. The researchers highlight that both organised and unorganised retail businesses co-exist and change as per the needs of the market. Due to financial constraints, customers prefer to buy high-quality products from organised markets rather than from mobile vendors. However, when the quality is uncertain, customers prefer to buy from organised markets rather than mobile vendors. The researchers conclude that, with respect to the retail sector in India, the country is at a crossroads.

Scope of The Study

The retail industry assists consumers in making a range of contemporary digital payments for their products and services purchases. Additionally, it stimulates the economy by generating income for the federal and state governments and opening up job possibilities. The unorganised retail sector benefits from the improved infrastructure of digital payments in several ways. Digital payments help attract foreign direct investment (FDI) by enabling the provision of higher-quality goods and services. The improved infrastructure of digital payments allows the unorganised retail sector to boost customer confidence in a secure and safe payment process.

Statement of The Problem

One of the information technologies in the banking industry that is expanding the fastest is the digital payment system. The majority of transactions take place via digital channels. The bank's staff members and clients will both benefit from this. The city of Hyderabad is the site of the current investigation. There are a great deal of commercial operations taking place there. It is among the cities with the quickest rates of growth. Thus, this research is being done.

Identification Of Variables:

The study's variable was determined by consulting the numerous literature reviews. The unorganised retail sector and digital payment studies conducted in India and other developed and developing nations were cited. Factors associated with the retailer's choice for digital payments was found to be influenced by these studies' assistance and use in this one the variables are: Age, Gender, Educational Qualification are independent variables. Manufacturer, Trading, Services are dependent Variables. Advantageous for businesses: clients may now pay at any time, from anywhere in the globe, without having to carry cash or visit an ATM; it's also easier and faster to receive paid, as well as transaction histories. People's awareness, lack of digital aptitude, safety and security, the origin of the fraud, payment channel coordination, and system hacking.

Objectives

- 1.To Study the advantages of digital payment methods in retail establishments
- 2.To study the attention of the issues that retail stores are having with the digital payment system.

Hypothesis

The following are the hypotheses that were prepared for the study:

- 1] H01: There is no correlation between the age of the clients and their use of digital payment systems.
- 2] H02: There is no correlation between consumers' ages and the challenges of the digital payment system.

Sources of Data: Both primary and secondary sources of data were used to create the current study. The study started with an examination of secondary data, which helped identify the

factors for the primary study and set the framework for the investigation. The auxiliary information utilised to construct the conceptual model by obtaining clarification on concerns that come up. Secondary information was collected from several sources, such as committee reports on digital payment methods like Visa and Watal Committee, which are propelling the expansion of digital payments, scholarly journals, and the Nandan Nilekani commission on digital payments, publications, working papers, news announcements, statistics, data releases, and official bank websites.

Methodology: Information for the study is gathered using both primary and secondary data. Secondary data is gathered from journals and websites, while primary data is gathered using the structured questionnaire approach. Descriptive statistics will be used for data analysis. The Chi-Square test will be used to estimate association. To do the analysis, SPSS version 23.0 statistical software will be utilised. To draw conclusions, statistical methods such as frequency, percentage, and mean are also employed.

Sample Size: The Sample size is 100 retail shop respondents from Hyderabad city in the total sample size used for this study.

Sampling Method: Data from Hyderabad city was gathered using a structured questionnaire (a collection of questions) and "Google Forms," which allows respondents to complete the form with a mobile device, a table, or any other internet-capable gadget. Among Google Forms' most important benefits is that because it prevents the responder from being able to, it guarantees that surveys are completed. should keep answering questions until every one has been completed. Individual approach was furthermore employed to gather information in order to address the non-coverage error. Not likely the data was gathered using a personal approach and judgemental sampling.

Reliability Test: Cronbach's Alpha: The coefficient for Cronbach alpha was computed. According to George and Mallery's recommendations, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient value for reliability statistics was found to be equal to greater than 0.50, signifying a moderate to high degree of internal consistency for our components.

Scale	No. of Items	α	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Digital Payments and major advantages	9	.96	.94	.96
Challenges of Digital Payments	6	.90	.86	.85
Hardware and gadgets	3	.87	.84	.88
Transaction fees	5	.82	.80	.83
Record keeping	4	.81	.80	.82
Failures and Delay	3	.79	.76	.80

The lower and upper bounds of Cronbach's α were calculated using a 95.00% confidence interval.

Outcomes for Linear Regression Using Devices and Hardware, Transaction Fees, Documentation, and Transaction Failure Failure Time Predicting Difficulties with Digital Payments.

Variable	B	SE	95.00% CI	β	t	p
Digital Payments	4.26	0.96	[2.41, 6.24]	0.00	4.41	< .001
Hardware and gadgets	0.51	0.10	[0.32, 0.71]	0.22	5.24	< .001
Transaction fees	0.30	0.06	[0.20, 0.41]	0.24	5.37	< .001
Record keeping	0.41	0.08	[0.21, 0.61]	0.19	4.61	< .001
Delay on transaction failure	0.40	0.06	[0.27, 0.51]	0.24	6.21	< .001

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Results: $F(4,517) = 314.18, p < .001, R = .70$

Unstandardized Regression Equation: Challenges of Digital Payments = 4.36 + 0.54* Hardware and gadgets + 0.32*Transaction fees + 0.43*Record keeping + 0.40* Delay on transaction failure

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Responses on the basis of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	68	68.00
Female	22	32.00
Total	100	100

The Above Table shows that 68% were male and 32.00% (100) female respondents out of a total sample size of 100 (100%). The majority of respondents can be observed of Gender was male with 68.00%.

Responses on the basis of age wise

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
Age	5	5%
Less than 30	36	36%
31-40	55	55%
41-50	4	4%
Above 51	100	100%
Total		
Medical shops	12	12%
Fancy	17	17%
Grocery shops	21	21%
Tailoring shops	12	12%
Vegetable shops	14	14%
Bakery	13	13%
Stationery shops	11	11%
Total	100	100%

According to the survey, 55% of respondents are between the ages of 40 and 50, 36% are between the ages of 30 and 40, 5 respondents are under the age of 30, and only 4% of

respondents are older than years. According to the study, the respondents work for a variety of retail establishments, including 21% grocery stores, 21% grocery stores, 12% each for medical and tailor shops, and 11% for stationery stores.

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

The different digital payment modes

PARTICULARS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS
Phone pay	64
Google pay	47
PAYTM	37
Internet banking	26
Debit card	59
Credit card	56
Amazon pay	14

Source: Primary Data

The study shows that above that 64 respondents use to phone pay 47 respondent use Google pay,37 respondents are use Paytm,26 respondents are use only Internet Banking,59 respondents are use debit card,56 Respondents use credit card.and 15 Respondents use amazon pay. Phone pay is mostly preferred by the customers for Digital Payment mode.

Findings

The good response indicated that digital payments are advantageous for businesses. Retailers rely on cash for a variety of business purposes, but digital payments make payments easier. Digital payments enable retailers to exchange payments at any time and from any location. Both transaction costs and time have been reduced by digital payment. Anyone may make a payment using digital means at any moment by holding a smartphone or using a card. It is not required to visit an ATM or bank, saving you time and lower transaction costs, which is the consumer's most convenient option. Those who use digital payments are better able to maintain their banking balance. mechanism and it also boosts the economy's credit generation. Among 100 respondents (84.23%) gave a favourable response, saying that consumers no longer must bring or visit an ATM centre in order to complete their transaction. With traditional payment methods, customers must be physically present to complete their purchase. They also have to have cash with them at all times, and the amount of money they can spend on a transaction is limited if they have cash in their wallet. It has a negative impact on the economy and lowers consumer expenditure overall. The majority of respondents, are concur that the country's mobile payment revolution has resulted in a surge in the use of digital payment by retailers. The creation of mobile applications for digital payments has been crucial. part in the growing number of users of digital payment methods. Numerous smartphone applications, such as Paytm, have been created for transactions. BHIM, Google Pay, and other apps created. Not just for purchases, but even on these mobile applications, users may access various services, such as bill payment, financial and saving practices.

Suggestions

Appropriate awareness campaigns have to be run for the clients so they may benefit hassle-free. It is important to advise customers to regularly update their pin numbers and passwords in order to alleviate their concern about hackers. Clients should be informed not to divulge their digital payment data to other parties. Customers now have more payment alternatives thanks to digital payments. That explains why there is a rise in internet purchasing these days. We now believe that making purchases doesn't require going to physical stores thanks to this online payment option. whatever. This is the easiest and most practical method for getting rid of all limitations on the use of products and services. Anything may happen at any time. be acquired. Consequently, the use of digital payments has boosted the purchase of Individuals. Hackers are using new techniques these days to perpetrate fraud. Retailers that are unsure about a customer's payment could contact the police or cyber cell to get assistance instead of getting into a heated argument with them. Retailers that look for transaction failure or payment-related concerns online shouldn't contact any unauthorised numbers. For them to obtain a real customer service number, they must go to the bank once. It is urged that retailers avoid downloading any programs that claim to recover deleted texts, calls, WhatsApp conversations, or files from unidentified sources. These days, hackers use these kinds of ploys and methods to compromise bank information. Fraudsters may occasionally ask you for your Wi-Fi or hotspot user name and password to access the transaction payment system. Thus, businesses have to stay away from this kind of information exchange with unidentified individuals.

- Retailers like Paytm should have a mechanism in place that allows them to configure when their money is received, eliminating the need to constantly check their phone.
- Retailers must remember not to divulge their payment information. with any unknown individual, particularly whether it's their account number, cellphone number, or OTP, debit card number, and so forth.
- Small shops may secure their payment credentials by avoiding using multiple payment apps. They should choose one payment app after considering the deals and advantages offered by the payment service provider.
- Retailers should continuously update their app with the transactions they make so that their credit card information becomes protected and secure.
- Store employees shouldn't provide their cell phones to strangers. The Mobile phone screen lock, email address, login, and payment transaction PIN Sharing the app with others is not advised. Setting up robust security is the best way to keep it. lock.

Conclusion

One of the fantastic innovations created by the banking industry is the digital payment system. A greater number of clients have profited from this. But not all clients are aware of the majority of digital payment method programmes. Therefore, all e-banking consumers should receive the

same information from bank staff. According to the survey, every one of the 100 participants wants to continue using digital payments in the future. However, clients should also be mindful of all transactions and notify the bank immediately if something is amiss with their account. In order for the appropriate steps to be done. It's crucial to use caution and safety while utilising digital payment methods. Retailers' top priority is ensuring the security of digital payments. There are still issues with digital payments that need to be resolved, such as low reimbursement, an excessive number of payment service providers, and lack of user uptake. intricate and costly transactions. Retailers believe that dealing with these issues and implementing more advantageous regulations would help boost consumer acceptance of digital money transfers. Conversely, retailers think that consumers' uptake of digital the amount paid has gone up over time. Given that the use of digital payments has encouraged people's purchasing habits. 82.02% of respondents concur that using digital payments boosts a company's revenue. For instance, it is evident that today's businesspeople all desire to utilise the internet. platforms for their business's growth and for their sales. Everyone is contributing. a digital payment method as, in theory, using digital currency will not cause as much suffering as it does when pay in person. Thus, when it comes to digital payments, there will be less financial awareness, which leads to in increased expenditure.

References

- Kohli, R., & Bhagwati, J. 2011, Organized retailing in India: Issues and outlook. Columbia Business School Research Paper, (12/25)
- Rana, N., Luthra, S., & Rao, H. R. 2018, "Developing a framework using interpretive structural modeling for the challenges of digital financial services in India".
- Alpesh Shah and others 2020, 15, Digital Payments 2020 India: The Boston Consulting Group: Google – The making of A \$ 500 Billion Ecosystem in India.
- Pal, D., Vanijja, V., & Papasratorn, B. 2015, An empirical investigation into the end-user adoption of NFC mobile payment systems *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 69, pp. 13–25.
- Meity February, 2019, 39, Digital Bharat, Saksham Bharat - A Compendium on Digital India. Retrieved from - meity.gov.in -<https://pib.gov.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=188832>.
- Radhika, K. P., & Devi, P. A. 2018, Use of Electronic Payment Instruments and Effect on Cash Management: A Micro Analysis. *Economic Affairs*, 63(3), 717-723.
- Kozar, A., Vasiljević, D., & Radivojević, M. 2017, Transformation of digital business by applying benchmarking. *International Journal in IT & Engineering*, 5(8), 6-16.
- BIS Working Papers 2021, Retrieved from–bis.org, <https://www.bis.org/publ/work973.pdf>
- Mishra, V., Walsh, I., & Srivastava, A. 2021, Merchants' adoption of mobile payment in emerging economies: the case of unorganised retailers in India. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 1-17.

Dhevan, K., & Vidya, M. 2018, Digital Buyer Behaviour in B2C Model-An Empirical Research Study in Trichirappalli District of Tamil Nadu. *Sumedha Journal of Management*, 7(2), 115-124.

Chandrasekhar, H. M. 2016, A Study on Organized Retail on Unorganized Retail Outlets in Mysore City. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 3(4), 11-22.

Zuo, L., Strauss, J., & Zuo, L. 2021, The Digitalization Transformation of Commercial Banks and Its Impact on Sustainable Efficiency Improvements through Investment in Science and Technology. *Sustainability*, 13(19), 11028.

<https://www.unionbankofindia.co.in/english/point-of-sales.aspx> Accessed on 04-09-2019.

http://cashlessindia.gov.in/internet_banking.html Accessed on 05-09-2019.

<https://www.rbi.org.in/SCRIPTS/PublicationReportDetails.aspx?UrlPage=&ID=243>
Accessed on 05-09-2019.

<https://www.rba.gov.au/publications/consultations/201106-strategic-review/innovation/issues/objectives-efficient.html> accessed on 11-10-2020.

<https://horasis.org./the-importance-of-digital-payments> accessed on 11-10-2020.